

“MODERN TEACHING METHODS”

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ANNOTATION

Nowadays we can meet the phrase “modern teaching” not only in teaching foreign languages, but also in all subjects of education such as mathematics, literature, history, geography, and other subjects of education. Simply said, modern teaching means to attract pupils by using new techniques, new methods.

Now English teachers have always been concerned about the inadequacy of conventional methods of English teaching in Uzbek education systems. The teacher of 21 century should use traditional concepts and techniques of classroom teaching and should adopt the recent and innovative teaching techniques.

Key words: *modern teaching techniques, problems in teaching, BST, types of learning.*

Theme: Modern Teaching Methods

*“The teaching method which focuses more on teaching the students for improving their intellect behavior by using various new and innovative ideas rather than making them recite the syllabus to clear the examination with the same old style is **Modern Teaching Methods** in simple words.”*

The new teaching method which we called the modern teaching method is more activity-based and centres the learner's mind which involves them entirely into the process of learning. In the modern teaching method, curriculum teaching and planning are done keeping the learner as the primary target.

Through this way, learners actively participate in the whole process to build their knowledge and sharpen their skills; this is also termed as a constructivist approach. On the other hand, the mentor or teacher only leads them and guides them to focus on the objectives of the subject. This is all done by engaging in activities and by adopting innovative modern teaching techniques. New demand of the era or the need of the hour for students is to embrace the contemporary teaching methods which will also help in reducing the competition among the students, promote cooperation, and boost the health study environment.

Brief Introduction

Over the years, there have been visible changes in teaching style. Opposite to the memorization and same old recitation practice to teach the students, now with Advantages of modern teaching methods, interactive methods of teaching have been introduced, and its result can be seen. This is an education reform which provides an entirely different angle of teaching and learning because modern teaching methods do not treat all students at the same level of their understanding ability, unlike the conventional method of teaching.

Rather than the only teacher based, modern teaching methods focus more on questioning, demonstration, explaining, practical, collaboration methods, and are more activity-based.

Why modern teaching is the need of the hour?

Education is the need of the hour as it creates a literate society and in the process of educating the society, motivation and instructions are very crucial and teachers, guides and administrators are responsible to motivate learners. The rate of literacy will be leveled up by providing education to the most parts of society.

However, with time being changed to an extent, learners demand new techniques and methods to gain knowledge which specializes them not only in theoretical study but ensures them to provide practical knowledge, sharpen their skills, and make them educated to face any kind of challenges. Modern teaching methods are the only way to meet the requirements of modern times.

Characteristics of Modern Teaching Methods

The modern teaching methods help to build or develop a productive understanding of basic science and technology (BST). Hence, the elements of contemporary teaching methods include:

1. Learner-centered

One of the essential characteristics of the modern teaching methods in basic science and technology (BST) is it is learner-centred. It focuses on learners while using or applying during classroom and laboratory lectures. The teacher acts only as a guide, and all the learning process involves learners. Learners significantly appear as a dominator in classroom interactions.

2. Task-Based or Activity-based

The teacher or guide of BST organizes activity or task and engages students to learn through this way. Hence it is an activity-based or commission-based. Students are offered or asked to take part in classroom interaction through these interactive activities.

3. Resource-Based

BST teachers should be resourceful. They should collect and distribute all the required study material to the learners for their learning or to understand the topic clearly. The resources can be collected from the school environment or any other place where it is available. Also, a learner can be the source to bring study material or resources from their end.

4. Interactive in Nature

One characteristic defines the modern teaching method as very interactive. The teacher asks the students to form small groups or work as individuals to perform the learning tasks and come up with the desired results. It helps them to gather knowledge from one another. Students learn to work together and a sense of cooperation. It also works in their favour when they step out in the outer world.

5. Integrative in Nature

One of the vital characteristics of Advantages of modern teaching methods is it is integrative. Teachers link topics of one subject, e.g., social science topics like drug use, domestic violence, safety, pollution, food distribution, crime etc. to other issues and make it integrative. By this, a learner can gain knowledge of more topics studying one.

6. Peer Collaboration

Modern teaching methods not only encourage students by allowing them to present their ideas or initiative by noticing their responses, studying their research, and allowing them to answer during interaction in BST classes but also selects students based on interest, needs, and feelings. Through Instructional activities, students learn to work cooperatively, and they appreciate their competitors' work as well. In the BST curriculum, learner's interests are considered most important, and they are guided towards their goals and careers.

Modern Teaching Methods are following:

Collaborative Learning

Earlier, when students were asked to revise the topic or syllabus during an examination or regular days, they used to revise the syllabus in isolation or at home. This practise was widespread in traditional teaching methods. To deal with this issue or provide a more useful platform for students, schools are coming up with collaborative learning. In this modern teaching method, teachers form a group of students where they can solve their problem, debates on topics, and clear their queries. This helps in developing social skills and allows students to understand the subject faster.

Spaced Learning

Spaced learning is one of the modern teaching methods, which is being followed by teachers. In this method, teachers repeat a lesson multiple times, basically until the students understand entirely. However, the teacher repeats the course with two 10-minute spaces (break) in-between the lessons.

The gap is meant to refresh the mind by playing physical activities or mindfulness techniques which prepares them for the next session of the same lesson. This method gives the students intervals to inherit the knowledge and create connections between learnings. Before moving forward to another chapter, this method prepares the students with basics.